

Red *Noctiluca* Simulator: Operation Manual

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1. Introduction

This manual provides instructions to operate the red *Noctiluca* simulator.

The file name of the simulator is: [redNoctiluca Simulator.sip](#)

This is operated with a free to end-user Windows PC application Powersim Cockpit. Installation guidance is provided in the **Appendix**.

The red *Noctiluca* simulator (**Fig.1**) is described within a 1-D water column in which the total mixed layer depth is divided into 1 m depths with vertical eddy diffusion between the blocks and across the ergocline into and out of the lowest block of the mixed layer depth. Details of the simulator construct are provided in Mitra (2025).

Figure 1. Schematic of the red *Noctiluca* simulator. The phytoplankton utilize dissolved inorganic nutrients (DI-Nut) and light for growth via phototrophy. A percentage of the dissolved organic photosynthate (DOM) is lost through leakage. Growth of red *Noctiluca* is via prey consumption. Inefficiencies in digestion leads to voiding of undigested organic material (VOM) and release of excretory products. VOM is assumed to be broken down by bacteria (not explicitly described here) and thence contributes to the dissolved inorganic pool (DI-Nut).

2. Homepage

On opening the simulator within Cockpit, the user is presented with the following screen:

The user has to 'accept' to proceed to the 'Instructions' page.

3. Instructions page

This page provides a short description of the different pages within the Simulator.

The buttons on the left-hand side of this page (indicated by a dashed green box) are present in the same location in all the pages within the simulator. These enable the user to switch between the different pages. The greyed button indicates the current page selection.

4. Controls page

NOTE: Although the simulator has been rigorously tested, it is not impossible that certain combinations of input values may cause the simulator to halt. If you encounter such a situation, please contact Dr Aditee Mitra (arkdynamicsuk@gmail.com), ideally with a screenshot of the slider positions causing the error.

The 'Controls' page provides sliders to enable the operator to configure the simulator for their investigations. The 'pause frequency' control panel ('pause freq. (d)'; indicated with green dashed box) allows for the simulation to be paused at either 5 or 10 day intervals to observe outputs (especially 1D) at these time points. At these times, the user may wish to alter 'Cloud' or 'Temperature' before un-pausing the simulation (Ctrl+space).

MLD	Mixed Layer Depth (m)
attco_W	attenuation of light in water column (m ⁻¹)
Cloud	cloudiness index where 0 = cloudless
T	temperature (° C; optimal for <i>Noctiluca</i> ca. 23° C)
NO3-	nitrate concentration (µM)
NH4+	ammonium concentration (µM)

4.1 Latitude

This slider enables the operator to select a latitude (° N) between the extremes of those of the British Isles.

4.2 Mixed Layer Depth (MLD)

The MLD slider enables the user to configure the mixed layer depth (m) between 5 m and 50 m to represent nearshore to offshore coastal waters.

4.3 attco_W

The variable attco_W (m^{-1}) represents the attenuation of light in the water column due to presence of coloured dissolved organic matter (cDOM). The value of attco_W may be particularly high in nearshore waters due to relatively higher concentrations of cDOM. Sources of cDOM include tannins from rotting vegetation and also products from sewage and water outfalls. The slider enables the user to choose a value between 0 and 0.5 where 0 represents pure water.

4.4 Start month

This input variable enables the user to choose a given time of the year to start the simulation. This affects the amount of light and day length. This function also makes use of the selected latitude. The scale runs from the first day of month 1 until the last day of month 12. Note that the ‘cloud’ and ‘temperature’ are set independently (see below).

4.5 Cloud

This input variable represents the level of obscuration of light by cloud where 0 represents total lack of cloud and mist. The maximum value 0.8 represents a heavily overcast sky.

4.6 Temperature (T)

The temperature (T, °C) slider provides a wide range of input options between 5 °C and 30 °C. The optimum temperature for growth of red *Noctiluca* is around 23 °C (marked on the slider with a red line) with no/low growth observed at ≤ 7 °C and death ≥ 25 °C (Hallegraeff *et al.* 2019; see also Mitra 2025).

4.7 Nitrate (NO3-) and Ammonium (NH4+)

The input variables for nitrate and ammonium are described as micro molar (μM) while plots are provided in units of $mgN\ m^{-3}$ or within the mixed layer as $gN\ m^{-2}$. The μM values for nitrate and ammonium can be converted to $mg\ N$ by multiplying with 14 (i.e., $1\ \mu M\ N = 14\ mg\ N\ m^{-3}$). The range of values for nitrate and ammonium are based on the values provided by Mike Best (Environment Agency) as detailed in the following tables:

Nitrate [NO ₃ ⁻]			
WB_Type	Mean	Minimum	Median
CW (winter)	232.00	0	9.00
TW (winter)	107.78	0	54.70
CW (spring)	21.84	0	5.32
TW (spring)	118.10	0	49.00
CW (summer)	16.20	0	2.57
TW (summer)	81.28	0	20.06
CW (autumn)	26.16	0	3.72
TW (autumn)	113.01	0	41.04
maximum =	232.00	0	54.70
minimum =	16.20	0	2.57

Ammonium [NH ₄ ⁺]			
WB_Type	Mean	Minimum	Median
CW (winter)	6.97	0.00	1.43
TW (winter)	14.32	0.00	5.86
CW (spring)	6.72	0.00	1.29
TW (spring)	17.10	0.00	3.71
CW (summer)	6.36	0.07	1.43
TW (summer)	12.11	0.00	3.21
CW (autumn)	10.54	0.07	2.04
TW (autumn)	15.16	0.07	5.57
maximum =	17.1	0.071	5.86
minimum =	6.36	0	1.29

WB_Type = water body type; CW = coastal water; TW = tidal water

4.7 Simulator Run

Once all the sliders have been configured, switch to one of the other pages (usually the *Summary* page), and press ‘**Ctrl+space**’ to run the simulator.

The simulator is set to run for 40 days. At the start of the simulation, the phytoplankton are assumed to be present at all the 1 m segments of the water column within the mixed layer, while the red *Noctiluca* is assumed to be present only in the deepest 1 m segment of the water column (Uhlig & Sahling 1990; see also Mitra 2025).

5. Summary page

This page provides summary information about changes in red *Noctiluca scintillans* and phytoplankton communities over the simulation time. The top panel in the Summary page shows changes in carbon (C) biomass (mgC m⁻³) and nitrogen (N) biomass (mgN m⁻³) of the phytoplankton (Phy) prey and red *Noctiluca* (rNoc) predator. The outputs show biomass at 1 m depth and, also the average values from the entire water column; the 1 m depth is chosen as this is the typical depth for sampling by the UK Environment Agency and, also the depth likely to be visible to the public. The lower panels show the changes in phytoplankton chlorophyll (mgChl m⁻³) and changes in red *Noctiluca* cell numbers (cells L⁻¹) at 1 m depth; the values from the entire water column in the mixed layer (average) are also provided.

A table with all the initial values as set with the sliders in the ‘Controls’ page is provided below the buttons (indicated with green dashed line). An example from the ‘Summary’ page is shown here:

6. 1D Dynamics page

This page shows details for changes in abiotic and biotic variables down through the mixed layer of the water column, as they change during the simulation. The X-axis indicates the depth of the mixed layer where 0 = surface.

A time plot of the average nutrient concentrations in the mixed layer is also included in this page.

The plots in this page are intended to be observed during the simulation run to appreciate the underlying diel (i.e., changing over the day-night period) dynamics. However, depending on the graphic processing power of the PC, these 1D plots may slow down the simulator. To advance through the simulation time course more rapidly, toggle between the *Summary* and the *1D* pages as required.

By pressing '**Ctrl+space**' it is possible to toggle between pausing and running the simulation. Use the pause option on the Controls page to halt the simulation at 5 or 10 d intervals so you can better compare results at that time on different pages. Use **Ctrl+space** to continue the run.

Pressing **F9** enables the user to auto-scale the outputs.

In the example shown here, the simulation time is shown as indicated by yellow call out box.

7. 1D Physiology page

This page shows details for changes in variables describing phytoplankton and red *Noctiluca* physiology across the water column as they change during the simulation. The X-axis indicates the depth of the mixed layer where 0 = surface.

Similar to the *1D Dynamics* page, the plots in this page are intended to be observed during the simulation run to appreciate the underlying diel dynamics. However, depending on the graphic processing power of the PC, these 1D plots may slow down the simulator. To advance through the simulation time course more rapidly, toggle between the *Summary* and the *1D* pages as required.

The top panel shows the changes in the phytoplankton chlorophyll-carbon ratio (Chl:C), nitrogen-carbon ratio (N:C) and growth rate ($\text{gC (gC)}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$). The lower panel shows the movement of red *Noctiluca* through the water column as the buoyancy changes with satiation (sinks following predation and rises following digestion of prey). The assimilation efficiency of red *Noctiluca* which is related to the prey quality; this is linked to changes in phytoplankton stoichiometry where high N:C indicates good quality food and low N:C indicated poor quality food (Mitra & Flynn 2005). Also, plotted is the change in growth rate of red *Noctiluca* ($\text{gC (gC)}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$) in the water column during the simulation time.

Even more so than with the *1D Dynamics* page, simulation outputs shown on this page reveal the changes that occur over the light-dark cycle.

In the example shown here, the simulation time is shown as indicated by yellow call out box.

8. Recording Outputs

For this demonstrator the way to record simulator configuration and outputs is via screen capture as shown in the Sections above. Alternately, each run can be saved as a 'new game' by clicking the 'save' button which will open a window as shown here:

This will preserve the slider settings as they were configured at the point of saving the 'game'.

Enhancements to this simulator could include export of all data to Excel for offline analysis.

For further information, please contact Dr Aditee Mitra (arkdynamicsuk@gmail.com).

9. References

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Appendix

The simulator is operated with a Windows PC application, **Powersim Cockpit**.

Cockpit is a free-to-end-user application that enables the user to run model projects that have been developed using Powersim Studio Premium.

Cockpit only works on the MS Windows OS.

To download Cockpit, visit <https://powersim.com/download-cockpit/>

IMPORTANT

If you already have any other Powersim Studio product installed, do NOT install Cockpit! The simulator should operate in other versions of Studio.

Once downloaded, follow the instructions provided by Powersim to install the software.

Note that modelling software makes intensive demands of your PC's CPU. Depending on the power of your PC, modelling can affect (slow) the operation of other applications that you may be running, and vice versa.

The shortest run time will be obtained using a PC with multiple cores (i7 and upwards) and having more and faster RAM. Good graphic capabilities are also beneficial.